

Development of a Small-Scale Wind Turbine

Olayinka Oladele Awopetu and Tunji John Erinle

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology
Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

E-mail: <ooawopetu@futa.edu.ng; authenticfaith@yahoo.com>

Abstract

The wind turbine, which produces virtually no CO₂ emission, has long been recognized as an abundant potential source of electric power. The fact is that wind power is one of the lowest-cost power generation technologies. In this work, a small-scale wind turbine has been designed and fabricated. The measurement, results and analysis of the wind turbine are presented in this work. The construction has been carried out successfully. The turbine comprises of three blades made of pipe, a DC dynamo used in place of an electric motor, a dc-to-ac converter, a hub that holds the blades, a vertical hollowed shaft, and nacelle that holds at the centre of the turbine. Four yards of electric wire is also used. This wind turbine was designed based on proper application of some factors that will aid its smooth running which include: the weather condition of the university, location, properties of materials used, satisfactory performance of the mechanism, economic considerations, and maintenance and repair implications. After the fabrication and assembly of the wind turbine, a test was carried out. The whole setup was placed on a surface of high altitude. After a few seconds, the blade rotates and 0.088 W was obtained, which is the average value. In all, the locally made wind turbine costs ₦64, 000 (\$ 400) to produce it.

Keywords: Wind, turbine, design, fabrication.

Introduction

A wind turbine is a machine used for converting the kinetic energy in the wind into electrical energy for other tall structures used for electricity power generation (Energy Quest 2012): “Blowing wind spins the blades on the wind turbines - just like a large toy pinwheel.” A successful early application of wind power (and one that still exists) is the use of water pumping machines (Dodge 2013). A typical windmill is shown in Fig. 1.

Theoretically, as the wind turbine extracts energy from the airflow, the air is slowed down, which causes it to spread out. Albert Betz, a German physicist, determined in 1919 that a wind turbine can extract at most 59% of the energy that would otherwise flow through the turbine cross section, that is, the efficiency can never be higher than 0.59 (Douglas *et al.* 2001). The Betz limit applies regardless of the design of the turbine.

Wind turbines of the modern type are used in wind farms for commercial production of electrical power (Gipe 2002) and are usually three-bladed and pointed into the wind by computer-controlled motors (Fig. 2). Modern electricity wind turbines come in four different styles and many different sizes, depending on their use. The most common style, large or small, is the horizontal to the ground. This turbine, and two or three blades spin upwind of the tower that it sits on (Wailes 1979).

Fig. 1. Windmill (Manwell 2000).

Fig. 2. Wind farm (Enron Wind Corporation 2002).

Factors Affecting the Wind Speed

The wind speed is affected by a number of factors operating on varying scale (from microscale to macroscale) which include:

Pressure gradient - This is a term used to describe the difference in air pressure between two points in the atmosphere or on the surface of the earth.

Rossby waves - These are strong winds in the upper troposphere. They operate on a global scale and move from west to south. The Rossby waves have a different wind speed to what we experience in the lower troposphere.

Local weather conditions - Play a key role in influencing the wind speed, because the formation of freak weather conditions such as hurricanes, monsoons or cyclones can drastically affect the velocity of the wind.

Use in aviation - In aviation, the wind speed is utilized to convert between the ground speed and the true air speed.

Reliability of Wind Energy

Wind energy is a promising source of electrical power because it is a clean and renewable resource. However, since the wind speed vary by time of day, season, and even from one year to the next, the wind energy is an intermittent resource.

With the growing worldwide demand for electrical power and the rising concern about global warming, many experts believe that the use of wind energy will continue to increase.

As wind power becomes an increasingly cost-effective source of electricity, the market for wind power should continue to expand. Some environmental and political factors, however, will also influence the growth of wind energy.

Materials and Methods

This section explains the materials used for various parts of the wind turbine with supportive reasons, design calculations, design diagrams and design analysis.

Material Selection Criteria

Some basic design factors are taken into consideration in the choice of material for the design of the wind turbine to enhance its simplicity, reliability, workability, stability and efficiency. Knowing very well the aims of this work, the design factors put in mind are:

Cost considerations - The materials used for the component parts in the fabrication of the wind turbine are relatively cheap and at the same time meeting the standard requirement for the efficient workability of the turbine. This factor also affects the marketability of the small-scale wind turbine.

Availability of material - The materials employed in the construction of the wind turbine are chosen from the locally available materials in order to reduce the overall cost of production and consequently making it affordable for local use.

Rigidity and weight - The parts are designed such that the wind turbine is rigid enough and has adequate strength to support its purpose or function.

Overall weight - The weight of all the component parts is designed such that the small-scale wind turbine is not too heavy and at the same time rigid enough to prevent deflection when the wind is blowing.

Table 1 provides details about the material selection of the wind turbine components.

Design Analysis of the Parts

The design analysis involves some constant parameters like density (ρ) of steel, mild steel, aluminium and plastic, and acceleration due to gravity (g):

- Density of steel, $\rho_{\text{steel}} = 7,900 \text{ kg/m}^3$;
- Density of mild steel, $\rho_{\text{mild steel}} = 7,900 \text{ kg/m}^3$;
- Density of aluminium, $\rho_{\text{Al}} = 2,700 \text{ kg/m}^3$;
- Density of plastic, $\rho_{\text{plastic}} = 2,200 \text{ kg/m}^3$; and
- Acceleration due to gravity, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The following basic design equations are used:

$$V = \pi D^2 l / 4 \quad (1)$$

$$V = \pi D^2 t / 4 \quad (2)$$

$$V = \pi(D^2 - d^2)l / 4 \quad (3)$$

$$V = l \times b \times t \quad (4)$$

$$m = \rho V \quad (5)$$

$$W = mg, \quad (6)$$

where: V is the volume of the materials, m^3 ; D is the outer diameter of the materials, mm; d is the inner diameter of the materials, mm; l is the length of the materials, mm; b is the width of the materials, mm; t is the thickness of the materials, mm; m is the mass of the materials, kg; and W is the weight of the materials, N.

Table 2 includes detailed calculations about the volume, mass and weight of the wind turbine components. Table 3 illustrates the determination of the wind turbine parameters.

Shear Force Diagram

The shear force/bending moment diagram is shown in Fig. 3. Here $AB = 840$ mm, $AC = 35$ mm, $AD = 420$ mm, and $BE = 180$ mm. It is easy to notice that

$$\text{Upward force} = \text{Downward force}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and } R_A + R_B = 17.6 + 26 + 2.2 = 45.8 \text{ N.}$$

Taking the moments about point B,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sum of clockwise moments} \\ = \text{Sum of anticlockwise moments}, \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

results in: $R_A \times 840 = 17.6 \times 805 + 26 \times 420 + 2.2 \times 180$, $R_A = 30.34$ N, $R_A + R_B = 45.8$, and $R_B = 15.46$ N.

The shear force at each point is obtained accordingly:

$$F_A = 30.34 \text{ N}, F_C = 12.74 \text{ N}, F_D = -13.26 \text{ N},$$

$$F_E = -15.46 \text{ N}, \text{ and } F_B = -15.46 \text{ N.}$$

The bending moment at each point is also obtained:

$$M_A = 0 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm},$$

$$M_C = 30.34 \times 35 = 1,061.9 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm},$$

$$M_D = (30.34 \times 420) - (17.6 \times 385) \\ = 12,742.8 - 6,776 = 5,966.8 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm},$$

$$M_E = 15.46 \times 180 = 2,782.8 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm},$$

$$M_B = 0 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm}, \text{ and the maximum bending moment, } M_{max} = 5,966.8 \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm}.$$

Fabrication Processes

The fabrication of a wind turbine is the act of construction and deriving a structure such as turbine that capable of producing wind energy to generate electricity. The turbine consists of a tower, turbine blade, circular disc with hub, nacelle and nacelle shaft, base with support, tail, rotor and rotor support, pillow bearing and pillow bearing support. Details about the fabrication processes are shown in Table 4.

Fig. 3. Shear force/bending moment diagram.

Table 1. Material selection of the wind turbine components.

S/N	Machine components	Criteria for material selection	Selected materials	Reasons for selection	Remarks
1	Nacelle	It should be able to withstand the eccentric motion of the turbine during operation.	Mild steel angle bar	It does not twist, easily withstand vibration and maintain firm stability.	Low cost and strength
2	Nacelle shaft	It should be able to withstand the stress and the weight of the nacelle and other components attached to it.	Steel hollow pipe	It has an ability to withstand twisting due to torque moment and compressive force due to weight of the nacelle and other components attached to it.	Durable and strong
3	Pillow bearing	It should be able to overcome torque from the turbine and the nacelle.	Steel	Easy adjustment and proper alignment	Low cost and reliable
4	Circular disc with hub	It should be able to overcome torque from the machine and the motor.	Mild steel plate, circular rod bar	Strength and proper alignment	Strong and reliable
5	Base with support	It should be able to overcome torque from the turbine and the rotor.	Mild steel plate, angle bar	It has an ability to withstand twisting due to torque moment and compressive force due to weight of the nacelle and other components attached to it.	Durable and strong
6	Turbine blade	It should be able to overcome torque from the turbine and the rotor.	Plastic PVC pipe	It does not twist, readily available, high allowable stress.	Low cost
7	Tower	It should be able to overcome torque from the turbine and the rotor.	Steel hollow pipe	Strength, rigidity	Strong and reliable
8	Tail	It should be able to withstand the eccentric motion of the turbine during operation.	Aluminium plate	Highly resistance to corrosion	Durable and flexible
9	Rotor support	It should be able to overcome torque from the turbine and the rotor.	Mild steel plate	Strength	Durable and strong
10	Pillow bearing support	It should be able to overcome torque from the nacelle.	Mild steel plate	Strength	Durable and strong

Table 2. Volume, mass and weight of the wind turbine components.

S/N	Machine components	Dimensions	Volume	Mass	Weight
1	Tower	$D = 90 \text{ mm}$, $d = 82 \text{ mm}$, $l = 1,450 \text{ mm}$	$V = [\pi(D^2 - d^2)l]/4$ $= 0.00157 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{steel}} V$ $= 12.4 \text{ kg}$,	$W = mg$ $= 121.5 \text{ N}$
2	Nacelle	$l = 840 \text{ mm}$, $b = 100 \text{ mm}$, $t = 4 \text{ mm}$, $D = 6 \text{ mm}$	$V = l \times b \times t - (\pi D^2 t/4) \times 2$ $= 0.0003358 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 2.65 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 26 \text{ N}$
3	Nacelle shaft	$D = 25 \text{ mm}$, $d = 21 \text{ mm}$, $l = 160 \text{ mm}$	$V = [\pi(D^2 - d^2)l]/4$ $= 0.000023 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{steel}} V$ $= 0.18 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 1.8 \text{ N}$
4	Tail with 2 holes	$l = 360 \text{ mm}$, $b = 230 \text{ mm}$, $t = 1 \text{ mm}$, $D = 6 \text{ mm}$, $t = 1 \text{ mm}$	$V = l \times b \times t - (\pi D^2 t/4) \times 2$ $= 0.0000827 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{Al}} V$ $= 0.22 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 2.2 \text{ N}$
5	Rotor support with 4 holes	$l = 180 \text{ mm}$, $b = 70 \text{ mm}$, $t = 2 \text{ mm}$, $D = 7 \text{ mm}$, $t = 2 \text{ mm}$	$V = l \times b \times t - (\pi D^2 t/4) \times 4$ $= 0.00002489 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 0.2 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 1.9 \text{ N}$
6	Circular disc with 6 holes	$D = 120 \text{ mm}$, $l = 1 \text{ mm}$, $d = 7 \text{ mm}$, $t = 1 \text{ mm}$	$V = \pi D^2 l/4 - (\pi d^2 t/4) \times 6$ $= 0.00001107 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 0.087 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 0.86 \text{ N}$
7	Hub with 3 holes	$D_1 = 30 \text{ mm}$, $D_2 = 24 \text{ mm}$, $l = 20 \text{ mm}$, $d = 7 \text{ mm}$, $t = 3 \text{ mm}$	$V = [\pi(D_1^2 - D_2^2)l]/4$ $- (\pi d^2 t/4) \times 3$ $= 0.000004744 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 0.037 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 0.37 \text{ N}$
8	Base (step circular disc)	$D = 250 \text{ mm}$, $l_1 = 15 \text{ mm}$, $d = 60 \text{ mm}$, $l_2 = 20 \text{ mm}$	$V = (\pi D^2 l_1)/4$ $+ [(\pi d^2 l_2)/4] \times 6$ $= 0.000793 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 6.26 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 61.5 \text{ N}$
9	Base support (3)	$l = 380 \text{ mm}$, $b = 100 \text{ mm}$, $t = 4 \text{ mm}$	$V = l \times b \times t \times 3$ $= 0.000456 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 3.6 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 35 \text{ N}$
10	Pillow bearing support with a hole (2)	$l = 80 \text{ mm}$, $b = 35 \text{ mm}$, $t = 2 \text{ mm}$, $D = 12 \text{ mm}$, $t = 2 \text{ mm}$	$V = l \times b \times t \times 2$ $- (\pi D^2 t/4) \times 2$ $= 0.0000107 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{mild steel}} V$ $= 0.085 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 0.83 \text{ N}$
11	Turbine blade with 2 holes (3)	$l_A = 525 \text{ mm}$, $l_B = 50$ mm , $b_A = 30 \text{ mm}$, $b_B =$ 20 mm , $b_C = 475 \text{ mm}$, $h_C = 60 \text{ mm}$, $D = 7 \text{ mm}$, $t = 4 \text{ mm}$	$V_A = l_A \times b_A \times t = 525 \times 30 \times 4$ $= 0.000063 \text{ m}^3$, $V_B = l_B \times b_B \times t = 50 \times 20 \times 4$ $= 0.000004 \text{ m}^3$, $V_C = b_C \times h_C \times t/2$ $= 475 \times 60 \times 4/2$ $= 0.000057 \text{ m}^3$, $V = [V_A + V_B + V_C$ $- (\pi D^2 t/4) \times 2] \times 3$ $= 0.0003711 \text{ m}^3$	$m = \rho_{\text{plastic}} V$ $= 0.82 \text{ kg}$	$W = mg$ $= 8.0 \text{ N}$

Table 3. Determination of the wind turbine parameters.

S/N	Parameter	Dimensions	Numerical value of each parameter
1	Total distance of tip travel	Rotor diameter = 24 mm	Total distance of tip travel in one revolution $= \pi D = \pi \times 24 = 75 \text{ mm}$.
2	Tip speed	Dynamo speed, $N = 512 \text{ rpm}$	Tip angular speed, $\omega = 2\pi N/60 = 54 \text{ rad/s}$, Tip linear speed, $v = r\omega = 0.012 \times \omega = 0.65 \text{ m/s}$
3	Tip speed ratio	Average wind speed in the university environment = 4 m/s	$TSR = \text{Tip speed}/\text{Wind speed} = 0.65/4 \approx 0.2$
4	Blade chord	Radius at tip, $R = 50 \text{ mm}$, Radius at point of computation at center, $r = 45 \text{ mm}$, Number of blades, $n = 3$, Lift coefficient, $CL = 0.85$, Tip speed ratio, $TSR = 0.2$	$\text{Blade chord} = (R^2 \times 5.6)/(n \times CL \times r \times TSR)$ $\text{Blade chord at the center} = 610 \text{ mm}$, $\text{Blade chord at the tip} = 549 \text{ mm}$
5	Blade angle	Angle of attack, $\alpha = 4^\circ$	$\text{Blade angle} = \tan^{-1}[(2 \times R)/(3 \times r \times TSR)] - \alpha$, $\text{Blade angle at center} = 70.9^\circ$

Table 4. Fabrication processes.

Parts	Processes	Tools and equipment used	Shape/Diagrams
Nacelle	Mark out the angle bar 840 mm length on the whole length.	Metre rule, scribe, try square	
	Hold the angle bar on the vice and cut to shape from the whole length. Drill 2 holes in it.	Hacksaw, blade, vice, drilling bit and drilling machine	
Tower	Mark out the steel pipe 1,450 mm length on the whole length.	Metre rule, scribe, try square	
	Cut to shape from the whole length.	Hacksaw, blade, work bench	
Base	Mark out the steel plate 250 mm diameter on the whole plate length.	Metre rule, scribe, steel rule	
	Cut out the shape from the plate.	Oxy-acetylene, cutting tong	
Base support	Mark out the angle bar 380 mm length on the whole length.	Metre rule, scribe, try square	
	Hold the angle bar on the vice and cut to shape from the whole length.	Hacksaw, blade, vice	
Circular disc with hub	Mark out the steel plate 250 mm diameter on the whole plate length.	Metre rule, scribe, try square	
	Cut out the shape from the plate.	Hand grinding machine, cutting disc	
	Centre punch the place to be drilled. Drill 6 holes in it.	Centre punch tool, drilling machine, drilling bit	
	Mark out the mild steel circular rod 20 mm length on the whole length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scribe	
	Cut out 20 mm length from the whole length.	Power hacksaw, blade	
	Machine the rod to 30 mm diameter. Drill it to 24 mm.	Lathe machine, machine tool, drilling bit	

Table 4. Fabrication processes (*continued*).

	Weld the hub to the circular disc.	Welding machine, electrodes, try square, slot hammer	
Tail	Mark out the aluminium plate 360 mm by 230 mm on the whole plate length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scriber	
	Cut the marking out size from the whole plate and drill 2 holes, then bend the plate.	Centre punch tool, drilling machine, drilling bit, bending machine	
Nacelle shaft	Mark out the steel hollow pipe 25 mm diameter and 160 mm length on the whole pipe length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scriber	
	Cut the marking out size from the whole pipe.	Hacksaw, blade	
Turbine Blade	Mark out the PVC pipe 525 mm length on the whole pipe length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scriber, try square	
	Cut the marking out size from the whole pipe. Drill 2 holes in it.	Centre punch tool, drilling machine, drilling bit	
Rotor support	Mark out the mild steel plate 180 mm by 70 mm on the whole plate length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scriber, try square	
	Cut the marking out size from the whole pipe. Drill 4 holes in it.	Centre punch tool, drilling machine, drilling bit, bending machine	
Pillow bearing support	Mark out the mild steel plate 80 mm by 35 mm on the whole plate length.	Metre rule, steel rule, scriber, try square	
	Cut the marking out size from the whole pipe. Drill a hole in it, then bend the plate.	Centre punch tool, drilling machine, drilling bit	

Results

After the fabrication and assembly of the wind turbine, a test was carried out. The whole setup was carried to the back of the engineering workshop and placed on a surface of high altitude (Fig. 4). The blade starts to rotate only a few seconds after installation.

The data shown in Table 5 were obtained using a multimeter to measure the power output. The resultant graph of power deviation versus time is shown in Fig. 5.

Table 5. Power output of the wind turbine.

S/N	Time interval (sec)	Power = $I \times V$ (W)
1	5	0.011
2	10	0.009
3	15	0.013
4	20	0.002
5	25	0.004
6	30	0.013
7	35	0.017
8	40	0.008
9	45	0.011
10	50	0.013
Total		0.095

Fig. 4. A small-scale wind turbine.

Fig. 5. Power vs. time.

Conclusion

The concept of generating electricity using the energy present in the wind is a workable one. However, the result obtained in this work is not exactly as expected because at times the wind speed in the university environment where the test was done was below the “cut in” speed required to produce the needed power output. The total voltage produced was 3.28 V and the total power output recorded was 0.095 W.

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